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Research Paper

INFLUENCE OF SOLVENT IN METAL ION CATALYSED REDOX REACTION

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ABSTRACT

Solvent plays a significant role in the redox systems catalysed by metal ions. In addition to the solvent these systems seem to be highly dependent on the nature and concentration of the metal ion vis-à-vis the formation of nanoparticles and the nature of the acid used. In this redox system the rate constant remains unaffected on varying the time of equilibration of the catalyst with the ingredients of the reaction system under different composition of the solvent. Activation parameters have been evaluated and a plausible reaction scheme has been proposed by presuming the interaction of transient metal ion with protonated MB as the rate limiting step. These aspects are very interesting and a detailed kinetic investigation on them is expected to be highly rewarding.

Key words: solvent, redox system, methylene blue

INTRODUCTION

Sulphur chemistry involving electron transfer reactions and metal ion catalysis has recently attracted considerable attention. The importance of sulphur containing amino acids in biochemical processes is well established. In various electron transfer reactions involved in the living systems, the participation of sulphur cycle plays a very vital role and actually the participation of this cycle is

indispensable as carbon and nitrogen cycles. A very important Amino acid such as cysteine and its oxidation product cystine maintain the integrity of -SH group in many enzymes and auto-oxidation of glutathione is responsible for its protection [1-3]. Cysteine has unique metal binding properties [4] and cysteine proteins act as part of "redox switches", to sense concentrations of oxidative stressors and unbound ions such as zinc. It thus provides a control

for the activity of metalloproteins and for signalling pathways [5]. Similarly o-mercaptobenzoic acid or thio-salicylic acid (TSA) has got its own significance and widely used as a model for enzyme papain.

Metal ions, act as the basic ingredient to regulate chemical reactions involved in transport phenomena and metalloenzymes [6-11]. The use of nitrosyl radicals alone or in combination with transition metals as catalysts has also been exploited in synthetic and mechanistic investigations [12]. Methylene blue, a thiazine dye has been used as a model oxidant to probe the electron transfer reactions involved in mitochondria [13, 14]. Recently, it has been used as a key component of a wide range of optical oxygen sensors used in the food industry for food packaging under a modified atmosphere of nitrogen or carbon dioxide (MAP) [15,16]. These fascinating aspects and the complicated chemistry of these reaction systems have prompted investigations on the oxidation of models biological substrates by model electron receptors such as methylene blue .

EXPERIMENTAL

The solutions of o-mercaptobenzoic acid or thio-salicylic

acid (TSA) and methylene blue were prepared by dissolving an exactly weighed quantity of the samples supplied by M/S Evans Chemetics Inc., USA in acetone and E. Merck, Germany in double distilled water respectively.

A fresh solution of the oxidant and the substrate was prepared in oxygen free distilled water. The solution of methylene blue (MB) was stored in dark as temperature and light affect its stability. All other reagents such as hydrochloric acid, potassium chloride etc. used in these investigations were either E. Merck GR or BDH, AnalaR grade samples. Double distilled water was used throughout these investigations. The runs were made in presence of sulphuric acid (ca. 2.0×10^{-3} M) because these are kinetically smooth and give reproducible results under these conditions. Moreover the rate of reaction was found to be extremely slow under normal conditions and thus, Cu^{+2} ions were used as the catalyst in these investigations.

The reaction vessels, made of Pyrex glass were coated black from outside in order to preclude the photochemical effect. The flasks, thoroughly cleaned with chromic acid and potassium bicarbonate, were steam washed and dried before use.

METHODOLOGY

The interaction of model biological substrates and electron receptors such as methylene blue will be investigated spectrophotometrically using ATI-UNICAM UV2-100 under aerobic and anaerobic conditions by measuring the decrease in the absorbance of the dye ($MB \epsilon_{660} = 6.76 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The n^{th} order rate constant (k) will be calculated by using the expression-

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \left[\frac{1}{(n-1)} - \frac{1}{(a_0-x)^{n-1}} \right] a_0^{n-1}$$

(where t = time, a_0 = initial concentrations of the reactants, x = concentrations of product)

STOICHIOMETRY AND PRODUCT ANALYSIS

Substrate and methylene blue are found to interact in a molar ratio of 2:1 and the empirical equation for the reaction may be given as-

The formation of the disulfide and the leucobase was confirmed spectrophotometrically by recording the absorption spectrum of the reaction mixture after completion of the reaction. These compounds were prepared by the known methods.

RESULTS

The kinetics of the reaction were investigated at different initial concentrations varied from $2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ to $6.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ of TSA. The concentration of MB ($2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) and other kinetic parameters was kept fixed. A plot of $\log [a^{1/2} - (a-x)^{1/2}]$ against t gives a straight line passing through origin with a slope equal to 0.44, which shows that order in TSA is fractional. It was found that the order in methylene blue depends on the concentration of TSA. At lower concentration (ca. $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$), the order in MB is 2 while the order is 3/2

in the oxidant in the TSA concentration range $3.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ to $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$. At higher concentration range $6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ the order in MB becomes unity. It is also seen that the rate constant has a tendency to attain a limiting value. It may be pointed out here that the variations in the concentration of the principal reactants were made in a relatively narrow concentration range (ca. 400-500 %). This was, however, necessitated due to the fact that beyond this concentration range, the runs became either haphazard or produce erratic results.

The rate constant obtained at different concentration of methylene i.e.

from $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ to $3.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ reveal that the rate constant decrease on increasing the initial concentration of methylene blue. The straight line obtained on plotting $\log k_{3/2}$ against $\log [\text{MB}]$ has a negative slope of 1.86 which indicates the participation of some inhibiting species during the course of reaction. It is observed that the rate constant increases slightly on increasing $[\text{H}^+]$ in the reaction system and attain a limiting value at higher concentration of sulphuric acid. The concentration of sulphuric acid was varied from $0.5 \times 10^3 \text{ M}$ to $4.0 \times 10^3 \text{ M}$ at constant ionic strength. A plot of $\log [\text{H}^+]$ against $\log k_{3/2}$ gives a straight line with a slope equal to 0.43 which indicates that the mode of participation of H^+ ions in the reaction system is not of a simple nature.

The rate constant increases linearly on increasing the concentration of Cu(II) . The double log plot between k_0 and Ru(III) gives a straight line with a slope of 0.96. It is pertinent to mention here that the rate of reaction is not influenced by the time of equilibration of the catalyst with other ingredients of the reaction system excluding MB which is in contrast with the observations made for Ru(III) catalyzed oxidation of cysteine with this oxidant [17]. The addition of the disulphide does not influence the rate but addition of the leuco base retards it. In order to account for the kinetic influence of Sn-

HCl couple, used to reduce MB; identical blank runs were made by adding tin, dissolved in HCl to the reaction system.

The runs were made at different temperatures ranging between 35 and 45°C and the heat of activation was evaluated by using the Arrhenius plots as well as van't Hoff isochore equation. It was subsequently used to calculate the entropy and free energy of activation of the reaction. ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* was found to be 38.2 KJmole^{-1} , -218.40 $\text{J}^{-1}\text{deg}^{-1}\text{mole}^{-1}$ and 77.21 KJmole^{-1} respectively

DISCUSSION

Methylene blue exists as protonated species as MBH^+ in acidic medium [18] while sulphhydryl compounds are known to form complexes designated as C with metal ions [19]. Further, Cu(II) metal ion has been used as catalyst in the oxidation of a variety of sulphhydryl substrates [20] and here too, a complex represented as C is presumed to be formed between Cu(II) and *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid. It may be mentioned here that the reaction was not catalyzed by adding Cu-TSA complex prepared externally to the reaction system which suggests the participation of some time-dependent species during the course of reaction. Incidentally, the existence of reactive species eluding an easy stereochemical interpretation has been reported in

literature and such species have been termed as reactive intermediates. The protonated methylene blue (MBH^+) is shown to react with another methylene blue molecule forming a dimer D.

The complex C may, in turn, react with the dimer forming a transient species C^* which may subsequently dissociate to give $\text{RS}^\cdot$ and half reduced methylene blue radical ($\text{HM}^\cdot$). It is pertinent to mention here that the participation of $\text{RS}^\cdot$ radical has been widely reported in the oxidation of thiols

On presuming the step in which C^* has been formed as the rate determining step, the rate of reaction may be given by the expression,

$$\frac{-d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = k_2[\text{C}][\text{D}] - k_2[\text{C}^*][\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{MB}^\cdot]$$

On presuming steady state for the species C^* and D and substituting $[\text{C}] = K_2[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{RSH}]$, the rate of reaction is given by the following equation:

$$\frac{-d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 K_1 K_2 [\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{RSH}][\text{MB}][\text{H}^+]}{k_1 k_2 [\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{MB}][\text{H}^+] + k_1 k_3 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 k_3 K_2 [\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{RSH}]}$$

The above rate expression explains the near zero dependence of rate on $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{TSA}]$, while it predicts a transition in order in MB from one to two. Under the given conditions, the reaction may exhibit an intermediate order of 3/2 in MB as has been observed. Further, at higher $[\text{H}^+]$, step (3) will be predominantly reversible giving a larger value of k_1 . This may lead to retardation in rate under such conditions as has been actually

while the formation of half reduced methylene blue ($\text{HM}^\cdot$) radical (analogous to semiquinone radical) by the action of reducing substrates such as ascorbic acid on MB, has been mentioned in the literature. The participation of free radicals in the reaction system has been qualitatively confirmed by the positive polymerization test with acrylonitrile. This will lead to the following sequence of steps ultimately giving the end products.

observed. The rate expression also explains a near zero order dependence of rate on $[\text{Cu}(\text{II})]$ at higher concentrations while there should be a linear dependence of rate on $[\text{Cu}(\text{II})]$ at lower concentrations of the catalyst.

CONCLUSION

These kinetic investigations clearly indicates that the system is very much influenced by the nature as well as the composition of the solvent. Runs becomes haphazard and erratic on

changing the composition of the solvent in the system. Such observations has also been noticed in the oxidation of model substrates by another oxidant 2,6 -dichlorophenol indophenol. This highlights the specific interaction of the substrate with metal ion in presence of suitable solvent which probes further investigation in the referred field.

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